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INFLUENCE OF VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY ON THE PREVALENCE OF DENTAL PATHOLOGY

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Annotation

Vitamin D plays an essential role in maintaining systemic and oral health due to its numerous biological and physiological effects. This publication discusses the influence of vitamin D deficiency and vitamin D supplementation on development, progression, and prevention of dental diseases.

Vitamin D is a fat-soluble vitamin existing in several biologically important forms: vitamin D₂ (ergocalciferol), mainly obtained from plant-derived food products and fungi;

vitamin D₃ (cholecalciferol or calcidiol), physiologically synthesized in humans.

Vitamin D₃ actively participates in bone metabolism and multiple physiological processes within the organism. Approximately 80–90% of vitamin D₃ is synthesized in the skin under ultraviolet solar radiation, while the remaining amount is obtained from food products such as fatty fish, egg yolk, and dairy products.

Vitamin D₂ derived from plant sources is absorbed in substantially lower quantities compared with vitamin D₃. Following hydroxylation, vitamin D₃ is converted into calcidiol, serving as the principal storage form of vitamin D and compensating for insufficient endogenous synthesis during periods of reduced sunlight exposure.

Depending on hydroxylation status, vitamin D may exist in active, inactive, or precursor forms.

Keywords

Vitamin D deficiency, osseointegration, dental implants, regeneration, bone metabolism, mineral imbalance, periodontitis, dental caries, implant osseointegration.

Introduction

Vitamin D is a steroid hormone synthesized in the human body under conditions of adequate ultraviolet solar exposure, typically within wavelengths of approximately 290–315 nm. Under the influence of ultraviolet-B radiation, 7-dehydrocholesterol in the skin is converted into previtamin D₃, which subsequently isomerizes into vitamin D₃ (cholecalciferol).

Vitamin D₃ is transported to the liver, where enzymatic hydroxylation forms 25-hydroxyvitamin D₃ [25(OH)D₃, calcidiol] — the principal circulating storage form of vitamin D [16]. Further hydroxylation occurs primarily in the kidneys, resulting in formation of metabolically active 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D₃ (calcitriol).

In addition to renal tissue, local 1- α -hydroxylase activity is present in multiple tissues including:

- bone tissue;
- placenta;
- prostate gland;
- keratinocytes;
- macrophages;
- T-lymphocytes;
- dendritic cells;
- cancer cells;
- parathyroid gland [7].

Excessive solar exposure may conversely lead to degradation of previtamin D₃ and vitamin D₃ into inactive photoproducts, thereby preventing hyperproduction of vitamin D in the skin.

Causes of Vitamin D Deficiency

Reduced cutaneous synthesis of vitamin D₃ and decreased serum vitamin D concentrations may result from:

- prolonged indoor stay;
- use of sunscreen products;
- cosmetic agents limiting UV exposure;
- dark skin pigmentation;
- advanced age;
- prolonged bed rest;
- wearing clothing covering most body surfaces [8].

These factors determine the importance of maintaining balanced sunlight exposure sufficient for vitamin D synthesis while minimizing the risk of solar injury.

Another important issue is limited dietary intake of vitamin D. Only a restricted number of food products provide significant vitamin D content, including:

- fatty marine fish;
- fish oil;
- egg yolk;
- edible mushrooms;
- dairy products;
- cheese.

Dietary intake alone is generally insufficient to compensate for seasonal reduction of sunlight exposure.

Average exposure to direct sunlight for approximately 15–20 minutes may provide synthesis of nearly 10,000 international units (IU) of vitamin D₃ [31]. Individuals with darker skin pigmentation usually require longer exposure periods than lightly pigmented individuals [20].

Role of Vitamin D in Bone Metabolism

Vitamin D plays a fundamental role in calcium-phosphate homeostasis, mineral balance, and regulation of bone metabolism [4].

Active vitamin D₃ synthesized predominantly in the kidneys under regulation of serum phosphate concentration and parathyroid hormone enhances intestinal absorption of calcium and phosphates while reducing their urinary excretion.

Calcitriol additionally promotes mineralization of bone tissue through multiple physiological mechanisms.

Studies investigating the influence of vitamin D on osteoclastogenesis have demonstrated both inhibitory and stimulatory effects [10]. Vitamin D regulates production of RANKL (receptor activator of nuclear factor kappa-B ligand) and expression of osteocalcin messenger RNA by osteoblasts, thereby influencing maturation and activation of osteoclasts [18].

Interaction between vitamin D receptors (VDR) and vitamin D suppresses RANKL-mediated osteoclast formation and inhibits osteoclastic bone resorption [1].

Furthermore, vitamin D:

- suppresses NFATc1 expression;
- enhances interferon-beta (IFN- β) expression;
- inhibits osteoclast differentiation [9].

However, the storage form of vitamin D — 25-hydroxyvitamin D — may exert stimulatory effects on osteoclast differentiation under certain conditions [24].

Vitamin D Deficiency

Vitamin D deficiency generally develops due to insufficient endogenous synthesis associated with inadequate sunlight exposure and/or age-related reduction of synthetic skin capacity.

Persistent vitamin D deficiency results in demineralization of bone tissue:

- clinically manifesting as rickets in children;
- leading to osteomalacia in adults [6].

Low vitamin D concentration decreases intestinal absorption efficiency of calcium and phosphates obtained from food products [38]. This subsequently increases circulating parathyroid hormone (PTH) levels, contributing to secondary hyperparathyroidism and disturbances of bone remodeling.

Secondary hyperparathyroidism associated with vitamin D deficiency increases serum calcium concentration through mobilization of calcium from skeletal structures by enhancing osteoclastic activity and increasing renal phosphate excretion [26].

As a consequence, bone mineral density decreases, contributing to development of osteopenia and osteoporosis. Another important manifestation of secondary hyperparathyroidism is phosphaturia, leading to reduced serum phosphate concentration and disruption of calcium-phosphate balance essential for skeletal mineralization [37].

In early childhood, impaired skeletal mineralization caused by vitamin D deficiency may result in severe skeletal deformities characteristic of rickets [5]. In adults, despite closure of epiphyseal growth plates, defective mineralization may develop in the form of osteomalacia accompanied by:

- reduced bone density;
- muscular weakness;
- bone pain;
- increased fracture risk [14,36].

Catabolic metabolic disturbances associated with vitamin D deficiency may additionally impair fracture healing and regenerative bone processes [33].

Role of Vitamin D Deficiency in Periodontal Diseases

Numerous investigations have demonstrated a correlation between severity of periodontitis and reduced serum 25(OH)-vitamin D concentration. These findings suggest that vitamin D deficiency may contribute to pathogenesis and progression of periodontal diseases [19,34].

Vitamin D deficiency affects functioning of immune cells and periodontal tissues [3]. Experimental studies in patients with periodontitis and diabetes demonstrated increased expression of vitamin D receptor (VDR) and receptor-type protein tyrosine phosphatase N2 (PTPN2) in gingival epithelial tissues under sufficient vitamin D conditions, whereas reduced 25-hydroxyvitamin D concentration was associated with decreased VDR expression.

Activity of nuclear factor kappa-B (NF- κ B), which regulates multiple mechanisms of innate and adaptive immune responses, is also closely associated with serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D levels.

Experimental models demonstrated that adequate vitamin D concentration suppresses expression of phosphorylated JAK1 involved in immunocytokine inflammatory signaling pathways [9].

Vitamin D additionally exhibits dose-dependent antibacterial effects against major periodontal and cariogenic microorganisms including:

- Porphyromonas gingivalis;
- Fusobacterium nucleatum;
- Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans;
- Streptococcus mutans.

Vitamin D suppresses growth of *P. gingivalis* by reducing expression of virulence factor genes such as:

- fimA;
- hagA;
- hagB;
- rgpA;
- rgpB;
- kgp.

These genes participate in bacterial colonization, destruction of host defense mechanisms, and tissue injury.

Furthermore, vitamin D inhibits activation of NF- κ B pathways induced by *P. gingivalis* [14].

Vitamin D receptor activity is also expressed in immune system myeloid cells and is associated with increased expression of antimicrobial peptides including:

- β -defensin 4A (DEFB4A);
- cathelicidin [30].

Vitamin D suppresses T-lymphocyte proliferation and decreases production of IL-2 and interferon gamma (IFN- γ) [17].

Deficiency of vitamin D contributes to reduced concentrations of anti-inflammatory mediators and cytokines within periodontal secretions, including IL-8 and CCL2 [3]. In human periodontal fibroblasts, administration of vitamin D increases expression of osteopontin and osteocalcin messenger RNA while simultaneously enhancing alkaline phosphatase activity, thereby reducing inflammatory destruction and tissue degradation [28].

Vitamin D and Prevention of Dental Caries

A large number of investigations conducted since the beginning of the twentieth century have demonstrated associations between vitamin D status and dental caries prevalence.

Early studies reported that vitamin D supplementation reduced caries incidence by approximately 47%. Replacement of vitamin D₂ with vitamin D₃ synthesized under ultraviolet irradiation demonstrated no significant difference in caries risk reduction [40].

Children receiving adequate ultraviolet sunlight exposure demonstrated:

- lower DMFS index values;
- reduced incidence of molar caries compared with children exposed to insufficient sunlight [35].

Similar results were obtained in children after ultraviolet therapy [29]. The caries-protective effect of ultraviolet irradiation is believed to be associated with increased endogenous vitamin D synthesis.

Modern studies evaluating serum 25(OH)-vitamin D concentrations demonstrated that children with higher vitamin D levels required dental anesthesia less frequently during dental treatment than children with lower vitamin D concentrations [23].

Marked reduction in caries prevalence was observed in children with serum 25(OH)-vitamin D concentrations above 50 nmol/L [31].

Silva et al. reported similar findings, noting increased risk of caries in permanent dentition among children with serum vitamin D levels below 75 nmol/L [25].

Higher serum 25(OH)-vitamin D concentration was additionally associated with increased mineralization of permanent incisor roots [19].

Assessment of Vitamin D Status

Serum concentration of 25(OH)D is considered the standard laboratory biomarker for evaluation of vitamin D status.

Generally accepted interpretation includes:

severe deficiency: <27.5 nmol/L;

deficiency: 27.5–49.9 nmol/L;

insufficient or suboptimal levels: variable according to guidelines;

adequate concentration: ≥ 50 nmol/L.

Currently, no universally accepted global standard exists regarding optimal serum vitamin D concentration [4,21].

According to data from the Institute of Medicine (IOM), between 20% and 100% of elderly men and women in the United States, Canada, and Europe demonstrate vitamin D deficiency [32].

The risk of vitamin D deficiency affects both children and adults. Women during postmenopausal periods and elderly individuals are particularly susceptible to reduced serum vitamin D concentrations [18].

Investigations performed in several European countries demonstrated that:

approximately 80% of young adults had suboptimal vitamin D levels;

27% demonstrated vitamin D deficiency;

15% exhibited severe deficiency.

These findings confirm the widespread prevalence of vitamin D insufficiency regardless of age group.

Vitamin D and Osseointegration of Dental Implants

The positive influence of vitamin D on bone metabolism and mineral homeostasis has substantial importance in implant dentistry.

Experimental studies suggest that successful therapy and improved osseointegration of dental implants may be expected in patients with adequate serum vitamin D levels compared with individuals affected by vitamin D deficiency [9].

Animal studies demonstrated that in the presence of systemic conditions such as:

chronic renal insufficiency;

diabetes mellitus;

osteoporosis,

administration of vitamin D improved osseointegration of dental implants [3,22,29].

These effects were observed predominantly in conditions associated with vitamin D deficiency [25].

Mechanisms identified in animal experiments may potentially be extrapolated to humans. Several reports have associated insufficient serum vitamin D concentration with early dental implant loss [14,39].

Clinical Effects of Vitamin D

In addition to its beneficial effects on bone tissue, vitamin D supplementation demonstrates multiple extraosseous positive effects [21].

Vitamin D administration has been associated with:

- reduced mortality from respiratory infections;

- decreased risk of type 2 diabetes mellitus [19];

- improved mood and psychological health [37];

- enhanced quality of life;

- increased physical performance;

- reduction of oxidative stress [25].

Although substitution therapy demonstrates positive effects in vitamin D deficiency, opinions regarding routine supplementation in healthy individuals remain controversial.

A significant number of investigators do not recommend universal screening due to:

- possible adverse effects of excessive doses;

- economic considerations;

- insufficient evidence for routine population testing [11].

Recommended Vitamin D Intake

The Institute of Medicine recommends a baseline supplementation of approximately 400 international units (IU) of vitamin D daily for all population groups and age categories.

Recommended daily doses include:

600 IU for children older than one year;

600 IU for adolescents and adults up to 70 years of age;

800 IU for individuals older than 71 years and people with increased skin pigmentation.

The maximal recommended dose:

1000 IU/day for infants;

4000 IU/day for children older than nine years and adults [14,25].

Exceeding recommended dosages may be associated with reduction in bone mineral density and increased toxicity risk [19].

For treatment and prevention of vitamin D deficiency, vitamin D3 (cholecalciferol) is considered preferable to vitamin D2 due to superior efficacy in increasing serum 25(OH)D concentrations [27].

Several investigations additionally suggested that vitamin D replacement may exert stronger extrasosseous beneficial effects in patients with vitamin D deficiency compared with individuals demonstrating optimal serum levels [33].

Animal studies likewise confirmed improved implant osseointegration following vitamin D supplementation [38].

Vitamin D Supplementation and Implant Success

Vitamin D supplementation may reduce fracture risk in elderly patients undergoing inpatient or outpatient treatment [29].

In individuals without specific risk factors for vitamin D deficiency, routine supplementation for osteoporosis prevention remains questionable [1].

In healthy patients, supplementation does not consistently improve bone mineral density or significantly decrease fracture incidence [6].

Experimental implantology studies demonstrated that animals with impaired bone metabolism exhibited improved implant osseointegration after administration of vitamin D supplements [13,24].

Local application of vitamin D directly onto implant surfaces has also been investigated. Multiple coating strategies for titanium implants have been proposed.

However, several experimental studies failed to demonstrate statistically significant improvement in osseointegration following such local procedures [16,27,40].

Conclusion

Based on currently available evidence, vitamin D plays an important role in pathogenesis of maxillofacial skeletal disorders and reparative regeneration following surgical interventions.

Despite contradictory findings regarding some aspects of vitamin D influence on inflammatory and reparative processes within the dentomaxillary system, continued scientific investigation in this field remains highly relevant.

Analysis of contemporary literature allows the conclusion that serum vitamin D concentration has substantial significance in dental practice, including:

- treatment planning;
- prognosis assessment;
- optimization of therapeutic outcomes.

Vitamin D deficiency should be considered an etiological and modifying factor in multiple systemic and oral diseases.

Patients with increased risk of vitamin D deficiency should undergo assessment of vitamin D status followed by preventive supplementation when indicated, especially during periods of low solar exposure.

Positive clinical effects of vitamin D supplementation have been demonstrated in patients suffering from:

- dementia;
- chronic renal insufficiency;
- depression;
- alopecia;
- tooth loss;
- periodontitis;
- osteoporosis.

Risk groups additionally include:

- elderly individuals;

persons with dark skin pigmentation;
patients with inadequate nutrition;
individuals with limited sun exposure;
pregnant and breastfeeding women;
children younger than two years.

The demonstrated positive effects of vitamin D on dental treatment outcomes make correction of vitamin D deficiency a promising and clinically relevant direction in contemporary dentistry.

References

1. Alkhenizan A, Mahmoud A, Hussain A, Gabr A, Alsoghayer S, Eldali A. The relationship between 25(OH)D levels (Vitamin D) and bone mineral density (BMD) in a Saudi population in a community-based setting. *PLoS One*. 2017;12.
2. Allard L, Demonceaux N, Machuca-Gayet I, Georgess D, Coury-Lucas F, Jurdic P, et al. Biphasic effects of vitamin D and FGF23 on human osteoclast biology. *Calcif Tissue Int*. 2015;97(1):69–79.
3. Allison RJ, Farooq A, Cherif A, Hamilton B, Close GL, Wilson MG. Why don't serum vitamin D concentrations associate with BMD by DXA? A case of being “bound” to the wrong assay? Implications for vitamin D screening. *Br J Sports Med*. 2018;52:522–526.
4. Aloia J, Mikhail M, Dhaliwal R, Shieh A, Usera G, Stolberg A, Ragolia L, Islam S. Free 25(OH)D and the vitamin D paradox in African Americans. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2015;100:3356–3363.
5. Bellavia D, Costa V, De Luca A, et al. Vitamin D level between calcium-phosphorus homeostasis and immune system: new perspective in osteoporosis. *Curr Osteoporos Rep*. 2016:1–12. DOI: 10.1007/s11914-016-0331-2.
6. Bouillon R, Prabhu AV, Luu W, Sharpe LJ, Brown AJ. Cholesterol-mediated degradation of 7-dehydrocholesterol reductase switches the balance from cholesterol to vitamin D synthesis. *J Biol Chem*. 2016;291(16):8363–8373.

7. Cashman KD, Kiely M. Recommended dietary intakes for vitamin D: where do they come from, what do they achieve and how can we meet them? *J Hum Nutr Diet*. 2014;27(5):434–442.
8. Christakos S, Dhawan P, Verstuyf A, Verlinden L, Carmeliet G. Vitamin D: metabolism, molecular mechanism of action, and pleiotropic effects. *Physiol Rev*. 2016;96(1):365–408. DOI: 10.1152/physrev.00014.2015.
9. Bikle DD. Vitamin D: production, metabolism and mechanisms of action. Updated December 31, 2021.
10. De Pascale G, Quraishi SA. Vitamin D status in critically ill patients: the evidence is now bioavailable! *Crit Care*. 2014;18:449. DOI: 10.1186/cc13975.
11. Gil A, Plaza-Diaz J, Mesa MD. Vitamin D: classic and novel actions. *Ann Nutr Metab*. 2018;72(2):87–95.
12. Giustina A, Bouillon R, Binkley N, Sempos C, Adler RA, Bollerslev J, Dawson-Hughes B, Ebeling PR, Feldman D, Heijboer A, et al. Controversies in vitamin D: a statement from the Third International Conference. *JBMR Plus*. 2020;4:e10417.
13. Halfon M, Phan O, Teta D. Vitamin D: a review on its effects on muscle strength, the risk of fall, and frailty. *Biomed Res Int*. 2015;2015:1–7.
14. Haussler MR, Livingston S, Sabir ZL, Haussler CA, Jurutka PW. Vitamin D receptor mediates a myriad of biological actions dependent on its 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D ligand: distinct regulatory themes revealed by induction of Klotho and fibroblast growth factor-23. *JBMR Plus*. 2020;3(5):e10432.